

A Method for Distinguishing Isomeric, Tautomeric, and Polymeric from Polymorphic Optically Active Substances.

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That a chemical substance may exist in two (or more) mutually convertible modifications has been known for more than one hundred years. Although Smithson Tennant (*Phil. Trans.*, 1797, 87, 128) had shown as early as 1797 that diamond and charcoal consist of the same element carbon, it was not till 1814 that Humphry Davy (*ibid.*, p. 557) accepted the correctness of this observation. But even after Mitscherlich (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1822, 19, 407) had noticed this phenomenon in sulphur and a few other substances, its appearance was still regarded as exceptional. At the present time, the number of such substances is very large. It is, however, uncertain whether the difference between them is due to a different molecular structure or configuration, or is to be interpreted as merely due to a different space lattice arrangement of the same chemical molecule. The former, in which the difference is one of chemical structure of the molecule, is classed as isomerism (including tautomerism and polymerism). The latter, in which the differences are brought about by different space lattice arrangement of identical molecules in the crystals, are grouped under polymorphism.

The two phenomena can be distinguished in the following simple way: If the modifications form a single independent component, they are polymorphic. The differences between them will be confined to the solid state only. When once the crystal structure is broken down, they will disappear. On the other hand, if the modifications form as many independent components, they are isomeric. The differences between them will persist in solution, unless tautomeric equilibrium has been established.

The methods, which have been employed for ascertaining the polymorphic or isomeric (including tautomeric) nature of the

modifications, depend on finding out whether the solutions given by them are identical or not. These methods will obviously fail in the case of tautomeric substances with a large velocity of change, as the solutions of the different modifications on account of tautomeric equilibrium will be identical. The tautomeric modifications will, therefore, appear as polymorphic.

Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 672) has made use of the above mentioned properties of the solutions of the two classes of substances, and has devised a method of diagnosis depending on the solubility. If to a saturated solution of the more soluble of two polymorphous modifications some of the other modification is added, the concentration of the solution will not increase, since the two forms give the same molecule in solution. If, on the other hand, the two forms are isomeric or tautomeric, the addition of the less soluble form will cause an increase in the concentration of the solution. As a measure of the concentration of the solution, Sidgwick determines the cryohydric point, using an ordinary Beckmann apparatus. The cryohydric points are determined for some suitable solvent for the two forms separately and then for the two forms together. If polymorphous, the mixture of the two forms will give a point lying between those of the separate forms; but if isomeric or (tautomeric), the point given by the mixture will lie below that of the more soluble form, the depression of the freezing point by the two together approximating to the sum of the individual depressions.

It may be mentioned that Bruni (*R. Accad. Sci. Lett. Art. Padova*, 1910, 26, 357) had anticipated Sidgwick's suggestion for the above mentioned method. He claims priority over Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 108, ii, 827).

The study of the properties of solutions of polymorphous and isomeric modifications of optically active substances furnishes a much simpler but equally trustworthy method of distinguishing between them. From what has already been said, it is clear that the rotatory power of each of the polymorphous modifications will be identical, whereas it will be different in the case of isomeric or tautomeric forms. It is, however, possible for the rotatory dispersion curves of two different substances to intersect at a point corresponding to some wave-length, and thus indicate identical rotatory power for them for that wave-length. The result will be that the two modifications, which are isomeric, will

appear as polymorphous. In order to get over this ambiguity, rotatory dispersion should be measured. In the case of polymorphous forms, the values will be identical throughout the range of the spectrum investigated. On the other hand, these values will be different in the case of isomeric (or tautomeric) modifications. This method is necessarily only applicable to optically active substances, and is, therefore, not so general as the method of Bruni and Sidgwick. It has the advantage that, as it is much more rapid than that involving freezing point determination, the possibility of the two forms (if indeed they are not polymorphous) coming to tautomeric equilibrium in the course of the experiment, is greatly diminished. It has the further advantage that a much smaller quantity of the substance is required for the measurement of rotatory dispersion than for the measurement of the cryohydric point.

The above-mentioned principle has been successfully applied in the diagnosis of the three forms of *o*-iodophenyl-imino-*d*-camphor* melting at 97°, 93° and 87° respectively.

(α) The lowest-melting form is obtained on condensing *d*-camphorquinone and *o*-iodoaniline in the presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate at 80-85°. When the alcoholic solution is cooled undisturbed in an ice-bath, light yellow prisms, m.p. 87°, are deposited.

(β) The intermediate-melting modification is formed when the temperature of condensation is higher (90-97°). It is obtained as yellow prisms (m.p. 93°) by dissolving the product of condensation in the least possible quantity of hot alcohol, and stirring the solution during cooling. As is shown below, unlike the form (α), this form does not change into the form (γ) when heated alone even above its melting point (*e.g.* 95°).

(γ) The highest-melting form is obtained when a saturated alcoholic solution of the form of m.p. 87° (α) is boiled for a few

* These compounds will be more fully described in a separate communication, in which the analytical results agreeing with the formula $C_{14}H_{11}ONI$ for each modification will be given in support of the view that these three substances are chemical individuals. The conversion of the α -form into the γ -form with or without a trace of the latter and that of the β -form into the γ -modification only in the presence of a trace of the γ -form by heat shows that these forms are three distinct substances and not impure specimens of one and the same substance. This is also borne out by the identical values of their rotatory power in three solvents for three wave-lengths (see Table I).

minutes, cooled and precipitated with water. It is deposited as yellow prisms melting at 97° . It is, however, more conveniently obtained by heating for a few minutes the lowest melting form (α) or for a longer period the intermediate melting form (β) at 75° - 80° with a trace of the highest-melting form (obtained from a previous operation) or by heating the lowest-melting form (α) alone near its melting point for a longer period. The reverse change by heat cannot be brought about:

It is thus clear that the β -modification is not a mixture of the two other forms, but is a definite third polymorphic modification of the substance.

The possibility of geometrical isomerism in the case of the different forms *o*-iodophenylimino-*d*-camphor is not excluded owing to the presence of the azethenoid group in the molecule, thus:

But the identical values for the rotatory power and rotatory dispersion of the three forms as given in Tables I and II definitely prove that those forms are polymorphous and not stereoisomeric.

TABLE I.
*Specific Rotations of the Three Modifications
of o-Iodophenylimino-d-camphor at 35°.*

Modifications.	Solvent.	Concentration. (g. 100 c.c.)	[α]		
			Hg _{gr.}	Hg _{yell.}	N _D
γ	Chloroform	0.7228	268.4°	215.2°	206.7°
β	"	0.7200	269.5°	216.7°	207.6°
α	"	0.7204	265.9°	213.0°	204.0°
γ	Methyl alcohol	0.7220	249.3°	201.6°	189.0°
β	"	0.7200	249.3°	200.7°	188.9°
α	"	0.7228	249.1°	200.7°	188.2°
γ	Benzene	0.4860	298.4°	235.6°	220.2°
β	"	0.7232	298.0°	237.2°	220.6°
α	"	0.7244	297.5°	236.8°	220.9°

TABLE II.

Dispersion-ratios of the Three Modifications of
o-Iodophenylimino-d-camphor at 35°.

Modifications.	Chloroform.		Methyl alcohol.		Benzene.	
	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{yell.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{yell.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{yell.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Na}_D}$
	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$	$[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{\text{gr.}}}$
γ	0.802	0.770	0.808	0.758	0.790	0.738
β	0.804	0.770	0.805	0.758	0.795	0.740
α	0.801	0.767	0.806	0.755	0.796	0.742
Mean	0.802	0.769	0.806	0.757	0.794	0.740

In Tables I and II, Hg_{gr} , Hg_{yell} , and Na_D refer to the green mercury line 5461, the yellow mercury line 5780, and the yellow sodium line 5893 respectively.

*The Effect of Polymorphism on Studies on the Relation
of Optical Activity and Chemical Constitution.*

When polymorphous substances are colourless and possess identical melting point, it is generally not an easy matter to differentiate between them. The substances may be chemically pure, but not physically so. The hitherto recognised physical or physico-chemical constants of solid substances are values which, in many cases, refer to metastable mixtures of two or more modifications of that substance in unknown proportions. Naturally no definite importance can be attached to the values of such constants, *e.g.*, density, refractive index, solubility, heat of solution, melting point, crystalline form, vapour pressure, etc. In the case of optically active polymorphous substances, the rotatory power is identical for the different forms. This constant will not, therefore, be vitiated as in other cases, by admixture with physically impure and metastable forms of the substance. It is, therefore, fortunate that the correlation of that esoteric property known as optical activity with the chemical structure of the molecule is, unlike other properties, unaffected by the phenomenon of polymorphism.

